

ASSESSMENT AND TESTING THE LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNERS USING MODERN METHODS

Alisherova Shahnoza Asqarovna

Faculty of Foreign Philology of the National University
of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek.

Master's student of English language and literature

Annotation: this article provided information on the assessment and testing of the level of knowledge of English language learners using modern methods, simulations reproducing realistic scenarios.

Keywords: learner, test, dictionary, feedback, quality, knowledge, basic program.

Assessing and testing the level of knowledge of English language learners is an essential aspect of effective language teaching and learning. English language learners come from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds, and it is crucial to measure their language proficiency to ensure they are adequately supported. Modern methods have emerged that incorporate the use of technology and the internet to make language assessments more interactive and learner-focused. In this article, we will explore modern methods for assessing and testing the level of knowledge of English language learners. One of the most widely used modern methods is online language testing. Online language testing is an effective way to measure language proficiency. These tests are delivered electronically, can be taken at any time, and provide immediate results. Moreover, they are adaptive, meaning that the test-taker's level of knowledge is determined dynamically, and questions adapt to their responses, ensuring a more accurate measurement of knowledge. Another modern method that has been gaining popularity is the use of game-based assessments to measure English language proficiency. This approach makes the testing environment more engaging and interactive, helping students to feel more at ease while testing their language proficiency. Game-based assessments are similar to online assessments, but question formats are designed in

such a way that they are presented as games. This not only motivates learners but also provides a more fun and enjoyable environment for testing English language proficiency. Additionally, digital simulations are becoming popular for testing English language proficiency. Simulations are designed to replicate real-world scenarios, giving students an opportunity to interact with the English language in context rather than as isolated vocabulary or grammar structures. This provides a more meaningful and accurate measurement of language proficiency, enabling educators to create learning opportunities that address areas that require improvement. One important aspect of modern methods of language assessment is the provision of timely feedback. Feedback can help students identify areas they need to work on and small corrections they can implement to improve their language skills. Timely feedback can also provide support and motivate students, enabling them to take greater control of their learning and make progress at their own pace.

The problem of monitoring and evaluating the knowledge, skills and abilities of learners in learning a foreign language has always been and continues to be relevant. There are traditional and alternative ways of measuring achievements developed by both domestic and foreign Methodists. In addition, age, the atmosphere of the proposed project, the purpose of the monitoring, the group of science, skills and competencies to be estimated, etc., need to be taken into account when choosing the type of assessment. The importance of the initial stage in education cannot be overemphasized, as it provides the basis for the formation of competences necessary for successful functioning in society (including professional) and adaptation to its changes. The standard sets out the requirements for the results of pupils who have completed the basic program of primary general education, which include the readiness and ability of pupils to develop themselves, and the development of motivation for learning and learning; mastery of key competencies, which are the basis of learning, and of cross-cutting concepts; the experience of participants in the study of a subject that is specific to the subject area in order to acquire, transform and apply new knowledge; as well as the system

of fundamental elements of scientific knowledge that underpin the modern scientific landscape of the world. Both traditional and alternative ways of assessing learners' performance are designed to: teach learners to evaluate their knowledge, to be more critical of their work; and to help learners to establish the limits of their own knowledge and ignorance; Increase in the personal resources of the trainees (attentiveness, effort, patience, strength, etc.); ability to compare their evaluation for work with the teacher's assessment.⁶⁸

In conclusion, modern methods of assessment and testing for English language learners have made language testing more valuable, efficient, and interactive. The use of technology, digital simulations, game-based assessments, and other tools provides a more engaging, learner-centered approach to language assessment. At the same time, timely feedback to individual feedback tracks progress, inspires student motivation, and helps learners identify where improvements are required. Through modern methods of language assessment, we can improve the quality of language education, ensuring students are adequately supported and receive the best quality of learning experience possible.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Matkarimova A. I., Tostemirov E. N. «Assessment in a teaching foreign language» *Young scientist*, 2017 (p. 432–434).
2. Semenova Y. I. «Manual on Foreign Language Theory: Web-based training manual» [Electronic Resource]. Kursk: CGU, 2014.
3. Adair — Hauck B., Glissan E. W., and Troyan F. «Implementing Integrated Performance Assessment».
4. Talabovna, S. S. (2022). Features of English and Uzbek comparisons in linguocultural aspect. *international journal of social science &*

⁶⁸ Хушвакова, Г. А. Methods for evaluating the achievements of learners at the initial stage in learning a foreign language / Г. А. Хушвакова. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2020. — № 19 (309). — С. 509-513. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/309/69650/> (дата обращения: 14.05.2023).